

ЭЛЕКТР ТОКИДАН ЖАРОҲАТЛАНГАН КИШИГА БИРИНЧИ ЁРДАМ КЎРСАТИШ

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Abstract: In this article, the author gives recommendations on how to save a person from the effects of an electric shock, disconnect from the current-carrying part, and turn off the voltage when a person is injured by electric current.

Key words: First aid for electrocution, voltage, non-conductive objects, gloves, boots, ax with a handle, electrical safety.

When a person is injured by electric current, he must first be saved from the effects of electric current. This is achieved by disconnecting the injured person from live parts or turning off the voltage. Voltage up to 1000 V is carried out by separating the person from the current-carrying parts, using a dry stick, wood, clothing or any other non-conductive object. If it is difficult to separate the person from live parts, cut the live wire with a dry-handled ax or other insulated-handled weapon. In sets with a voltage higher than 1000 V, isolation of the injured person is carried out using an insulated bar or cable, dielectric gloves and boots. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that touching a person under the influence of electricity without taking electrical safety measures is dangerous for the rescuer himself. The main condition for success in helping an injured person is the speed of help, because it is impossible to save a person's heart after five minutes of paralysis. If the injured person is at a height, before turning off the voltage, it is necessary to ensure his safety. In all cases of electric shock, regardless of the condition of the injured person, it is necessary to consult a doctor. After saving a person from the effects of electric current, it is necessary to determine his condition. If the injured person is conscious, it is necessary to put him in a comfortable position and keep him calm until the doctor arrives, and constantly monitor his breathing and heartbeat. If the injured person is unconscious, but breathing and heart is beating, he should be laid down in a comfortable position, collar buttons and waist belt should be removed, and instead, a cotton pad soaked in alcohol should be sprayed with water on his face and burned peacefully. Breathing and cardiac arrest are the most serious consequences of electric shock. If the injured person is not breathing but the heart is beating, artificial respiration should be started.

If the heartbeat has stopped, it is necessary to perform external massage of the heart along with artificial respiration. The most effective way to give artificial respiration is to blow air through the mouth or nose of the injured person. In this case, the injured person is placed on the ground with his back, wrapped in clothes or something else, and the neck is bent back, the mouth is cleaned of water, and the tongue is pulled out.

The injured person's nose is pinched, the person helping by placing a dry handkerchief or gauze napkin on the mouth and nose takes two or three deep breaths and blows air into the injured person's mouth. The frequency of artificial respiration should not exceed 12...14 times per minute, as it corresponds to the natural breathing rhythm. Artificial respiration should be

continued until the rhythmic breathing of the injured person is restored. Artificial respiration devices have been released in the industry. This device kit includes a mask and different sizes of air blowers (for adults and teenagers, children). If the injured person does not have a heartbeat, external heart massage is performed.

For this, the injured person is laid on his back on a hard flat surface, and his front buttons are unbuttoned and his chest is exposed. The helper presses the chest in the direction of the spine, placing one hand on the desired place of the chest with the palm, and the other hand on the hand placed on the chest with the palm. In this case, the chest is pressed only in an upright position to a depth of 3-4 cm with a frequency of 60 times per minute. In such a pressure from the chest, the blood squeezed from the heart enters the blood vessels. Care must be taken not to damage the rib while massaging the heart.

The effectiveness of the massage is evaluated by the appearance of a pulse in the blood vessels of the large artery. In most cases, cardiac massage of injured people is carried out along with giving them artificial respiration. In this case, artificial respiration should be performed during chest compressions. It is better if two people do this, one person will press the chest 4-5 times, then the second person will blow air into the injured person's lungs. This process is repeated in this case. A medical worker will have experiences of an effective way to restore heart function. For this purpose, special devices called defibrillators are used, and with their help, a short electric charge of high voltage is generated through the heart, which causes a general contraction of the heart muscles.

Burns occur when the skin is exposed to high temperatures (thermal) and when exposed to acids and alkalis (chemical). Burns are divided into four degrees according to severity. In the first degree burn, reddening of the skin is observed, swelling occurs in it, blisters appear in the second degree, blisters appear in the second degree, the skin dies in the third degree, and the skin turns into coal in the fourth degree. In case of a first-degree burn, the burned area of the skin is moistened with a stream of clean water, cold dairy products (yogurt, sour cream, etc.), cologne, a weak solution of vodka or manganese, 70% alcohol. In second- and third-degree burns, the skin is bandaged with an antimicrobial material. It is impossible to break the blisters full of fluid and separate the places where the clothes are stuck.

Extreme caution is required when separating burnt areas of the body from clothing. In such cases, when removing the clothes, the burned area of the body should not get wet or dirty. When the eyes are burned by an electric arc, it should be rinsed with a 2% boric acid solution. Under the influence of acids and alkalis, the burned area of the body is rinsed with cold water for 12...20 minutes. Then, in the case of acid burns, it is rinsed with a soda solution, and in the case of alkali burns, it is rinsed with a weak solution of vinegar or boric acid. A fourth-degree burn causes severe skin damage, and it can also cause the injured person to faint. In this case, sedation leads to loss of consciousness. As a result, it is difficult to detect a pulse, the eyes are spinning, breathing is fast and shallow, sometimes sensitivity is lost, and a person suddenly turns pale. In case of such a burn, the first aid before the doctor consists of the following: the injured person is carefully removed from the remaining clothes that are stuck to the burned area. Pieces of clothing are not pulled out, but cut with scissors from the border of the burn. A sterile bandage is applied to the skin treated with a weak solution of manganese.

After providing first aid to a doctor, the injured person is quickly taken to a medical facility. Cases of frostbite are mainly observed when working outdoors in the cold season of the year. Frostbite is divided into four levels. In first-degree frostbite, the skin is pale and swollen, and

its sensitivity is reduced. Characteristic symptoms of secondary frostbite are blisters of bright colored liquid appear on the skin. In third-degree frostbite, there is death of the skin, blisters filled with bloody fluids, and in fourth-degree frostbite, death of all soft tissues is observed.

In first-degree frostbite, the body is rubbed with a clean soft material until the affected area becomes red or warm. Then the affected area of the skin is wiped with cologne or vodka and bandaged with a heated germicidal material. It is not recommended to rub cold skin with snow, as it can cause skin damage and infection. When a large part of the skin is hit by cold and the whole body heals significantly, it is recommended to the injured person to take a hot bath. At the same time, it is necessary to massage him and rub his whole body.

At this time, the injured person can drink hot tea or coffee. In the case of second and fourth degree frostbite, the damaged skin should be bandaged with a material that kills microbes, and the injured person should be taken to a medical facility. In severe cases, if the injured person does not show signs of life, artificial respiration is recommended. In production conditions, poisoning occurs when toxic gases, liquids or dust enter the body. Carbon monoxide poisoning occurs when heating equipment is used incorrectly.

The exhaust gas from internal combustion engines also contains a large amount of carbon monoxide. Carbon monoxide poisoning can cause headaches, dizziness, nausea, shortness of breath, and in severe cases, disorientation and loss of consciousness. When the symptoms of poisoning are noticed, the injured person should be taken out to fresh air, a cold compress should be applied to the head, and alcohol should be smelled. If the injured person wants to record, he should lie down next to him. If he loses consciousness, he should immediately call a doctor and give artificial respiration until he arrives. When the symptoms of poisoning with toxic chemicals are noticed, the injured person should be given first aid immediately. In case of any poisoning, first of all, measures should be taken to stop the entry of poisons into the body.

If poisoning occurs in the room, it is necessary to remove the injured person to fresh air, remove the clothes contaminated with toxic chemicals. If the poison entered the body through the throat, the injured person should drink several glasses of warm water or a weak solution of manganese, and then vomit. After vomiting, to eliminate the poison, the injured person needs to drink half a glass of water with 2-3 tablespoons of activated charcoal. The mentioned actions are applied regardless of the type of poison.

If the type of poison is clear, depending on its composition, additional measures are used. As a result, the substance injected into the stomach neutralizes the effect of the poison. When toxic chemicals come into contact with the skin, it is necessary to wash thoroughly with soap and water or remove the poison with a gauze cloth without rubbing it on the skin, and then wash it with cold water or a weak alkaline solution.

References:

1. N.R. Ochilova, G. S. Muratova, D.R Karshieva. The Importance of Water Quality and Quantity in Strengthening the Health and Living Conditions of the Population. Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences 2 (5), 399-402. 2021.
2. М.Р Амонов, Р.А Исматова, Д.Р Каршиева, Н.Р Очилова. Разработка нового состава шликтующей композиции. Материалы международной научной конференции «Инновационные решения инженерно.2019.

3. А.А

Мажидов, Д.Р Каршиева, Н.Р Очилова. Физико-механические свойства напечатанных хлопчатобумажных тканей с загусткой на основе модифицированного крахмала, с карбоксиметилцеллюлозой и серицином. *Universum: технические науки*, 33-37.2019.

4. A.N Asadulloev, N.R Ochilova, O.G Jabbarova. Healthy lifestyle. *ACADEMICIA: An international multidisciplinary research journal* 11 (1), 1835. 2021.

5. Ф.Б Ибрагимова, М.Р Амонов, Н.Р Очилова. Ресурсосберегающая технология получения загустителя печатных красок с использованием полимерной композиции на основе крахмала, серицина и полиакриламида. *Universum: технические науки*, 18-21. 2017.

6. N Ochilova. Очистка сточных вод промышленных предприятий. *центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz)* 1 (1). 2021.

7. Н.Р Очилова. Внедрение в практику преподавания элементов проблемного и программированного обучения. *Молодой ученый*, 188-190. 2018.

8. Н.Р Очилова. Исследование физико-химических особенностей рисового крахмала как основного компонента текстильно вспомогательных веществ. *Учёный XXI века*, 27-29. 2016.

9. Muratova G.S., Mardonova S.M. Printing and technical properties of cotton fabrics printed by thickening polymer compositions. *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*. 2019.

10. Mardonova S.M. Efficiency of creation and use of multimedia training courses in the education system. *Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz)* 8 (8). 2021.

11. Mardonova S.M. Emergency Medical Care in Emergency Situations. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*. 2022. 28-29.

12. Mardonova S.M. Абу Али Ибн Сино асарларида маънавий-ахлоқий тарбия масалалари ва инсон камолоти. *Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz)* 8 (8). 2021.

13. Mardonova S.M. Соғлом авлодни тарбиялашда оилада соғлом муҳитни яратиш. *центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz)* 8 (8). 2021.

14. Mardonova S.M. The influence of bad habits on the human body. *центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz)* 8 (8). 2021

15. Mardonova S.M. Development of lexical-semantic groups of verbs and directional verbs used in old english. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022. 242-245.

16. M.A. Saitmuratov, N.Z. Zhalilov, S.M. Mardonova, U.S. Ergasheva. Structure of children's disability and the efficiency of rehabilitation (On the example of kashkadarya region). *Archive of Conferences*, 70-73. 2022.

17. Р.И Шарофутдинова, Г.С Муратова, М.Т. Турсунбаева. Концепции экологического мышления и образования и их формирование в сознании студентов. *Биология и интегративная медицина*, 156-161

18. N.R. Ochilova, G.S. Muratova, D.R. Karshieva. The Importance of Water Quality and Quantity in Strengthening the Health and Living Conditions of the Population. *Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences* 2 (5), 399-402.

19. Муратова.Г.С, Шарофутдинова Р.И, Турсунбаева.М. Талабаларда экологик тафаккур ва тарбия тушунчаларини шакллантириш. *Тиббиётда янги кун* 1 (1(29)), 105-107

20. Муратова.Г.С, Шарофутдинова Р.И, Турсунбаева.М. Concepts of ecological thinking and education and their formation in the minds of students. *Биология и интегративная медицина*, 156-161

21. N.R

Ochilova, G.S Muratova, D.R Karshieva. The Importance of Water Quality and Quantity in Strengthening the Health and Living Conditions of the Population. Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences 2 (5), 399-402

22. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, МТК Турсунбаева. Экологик таълим ва тарбия тушунчаларини шакллантириш тамойиллари. Биология и интегративная медицина

23. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, Г.А Жумаева, Ш.А Мустафаева Спорт тиббиёти фанидан амалий машгулотлар ўтказишда хамкорлик таълими усулларидан фойдаланиш-" Современное состояние, проблемы и перспективы медицинского образования.

24. Г.С Муратова. Основы психологии общения медицинской сестры. Young scientists' and mentors' non-standart congress, 177-180.

25. S.R Infarovna, M.G Saitovna. Role formation of ecological thinking and education in higher education institutions. ACADEMICIA: An international multidisciplinary research journal 11 (2), 1400

26. Р.И.Шарофутдинова, Г.С.Муратова. Concepts of ecological thinking and education and their formation in the minds of students. Биология интегративная медицина электронный научный журнал, 156.

27. G. Muratova. Влияние гастроэзофагеальной рефлюксной болезни на проявления клинического статуса бронхиальной астмы. центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 1 (1)

28. Z.H. Tolibova, D.R. Qarshiyeva, N.R. Ochilova. The role of Human healthy and safe lifestyle in the period of global pandemic-covid 19. The American journal of applied scincer 2 (11)

29. G.S. Muratova, D.R. Qarshiyeva. Basic Symptoms of Infectious Diseases European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630) 13, 117-121.

30. R.I Sharofutdinova, A.N. Asadullaev, Z.X. Tolibova. The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences 2 (5), 376-379.